

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF USING AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH IN THE FORMATION OF BASIC COMPETENCES IN GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the pedagogical conditions for using an integrative approach in the formation of basic competencies in students.

Today's development requires a new approach to the development of the general culture of society and the individual. This is evident in the social importance of applying the competence approach to the content of education. Education should be updated according to the needs of the individual and society. Development of theoretical knowledge and practical experience of the young generation is gaining priority in the educational process. In the course of education, the knowledge, skills, abilities, outlook, and behavior of each student are formed and serve to ensure the socio-economic, cultural and spiritual development of the society. A person develops in the process of education. The individual, in turn, ensures the development of the society. The educational system is tasked with forming a well-rounded person with certain personal qualities and competencies. Such a person should be formed as a self-developing, active citizen who can establish effective communication with members of the society, has the experience of general cultural activity, can make independent decisions.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The young generation is required to enter into mutual cooperation, respect cultural values, and develop the qualities of tolerance. In the process of education, students first of all learn the centuries-old social experience of the people. Therefore, this process serves to form basic competencies in students. They will have the opportunity to use the acquired social experience in their future activities. On the basis of universal human values, students develop the skills of critical thinking, creativity, and moral and ethical behavior. In researches in the fields of philosophy, sociology, pedagogy, psychology, the educational process is evaluated as a process of inculcating the social experience of the people. According to its nature, education is a pedagogical process directed towards a specific goal. In this process, students are educated, develop, acquire knowledge and competencies necessary for life. These knowledge and competencies ensure successful socialization of students.

The issue of socialization of the individual today attracts the attention of not only pedagogues, but also philosophers, sociologists, psychologists. The results of the analysis of many approaches and teachings show that in order to ensure the successful socialization of a person,

the formation of basic competencies is required. Basic competences ensure successful socialization of a person and strengthen his position in society. Successful formation of a person on the basis of mastery of basic competencies paves the way for his active participation in the cultural and educational life of society. Society itself is the main subject that socializes a person. He has the ability to adapt each person to his image. In addition, the society affects the socialization of the individual. In the process of education, students are integrated into society. Accordingly, a person must have basic competencies to function in society. Each person learns the values that are important for him in the process of communication. Basic competencies serve to satisfy students' motivational system and needs. With the help of basic competencies, students learn the norms of etiquette, cultural knowledge and values, spiritual and moral knowledge of the society they belong to. They acquire certain values and cultural-educational approaches in the process of communication with people who are important to them, i.e. teachers, parents, peers.

On the one hand, socialization is not a complicated process, it reflects a person's field of activity, his character and uniqueness.

The activity and uniqueness of a person represent his social functions, basic competencies. A person with basic competencies takes an active part in the life of society and has a positive influence on its development. A person's ability to actively participate in the life of society directly depends on the competencies formed in him. With the help of basic competencies, a person understands the essence of cultural and material wealth, assimilates it, enters into interpersonal communication, shows his civic position, learns scientific and technical achievements and uses them in his place.

Well-known specialists B.G.Ananov, A.N.Leontev say that in the process of spiritual development, a person absorbs all the wealth of the culture and enlightenment created in the human society, acquires existing experiences. A socialized person has the ability to eliminate all the means and factors that have a negative impact on others. Such a person develops himself, carries out his activities, and can realize his creative abilities.

As a result of the formation of basic competencies, a socialized person can have a positive impact on the environment, realize the social essence of his activity and contribute to the development of the cultural and spiritual life of the society. Socialization means that a person enters the world of interpersonal relations and culture. Basic competencies help him in this. Basic competences are formed as a result of students' assimilation of social and cultural norms and knowledge necessary for life in the educational process at various stages of activity. Basic competences serve to form interpersonal and internal relations and perspectives of a person. This, in turn, helps the self-development of the basic competencies of the individual, entering into communicative relations, mastering of cultural experiences. Basic competencies appear as a result of the educational process and as a pedagogical tool that ensures the successful socialization of students. The more effectively basic competencies are formed in students, the faster their socialization will be. With the help of basic competencies, students can easily adapt to various social situations.

The more effectively students' basic competencies are formed, the more easily they adapt to complex conditions and show social activity.

Pupils who have mastered the basic competencies will have the opportunity to make the right decision in different life situations, evaluate their behavior appropriately, and change the current situation in a positive way. When basic competencies are formed based on an integrative approach, students' practical skills in different areas complement each other. In the state educational standards based on the competence approach, the task of forming basic competencies in students during the teaching of all academic subjects is set. Because basic competencies serve as a basis for successful socialization of students and effective acquisition of subject-related competencies. That is why the process of formation of basic competencies presented to students based on an integrative approach should be pedagogically convenient.

One of the important tasks facing specialists is to develop effective mechanisms for forming basic competencies in students.

As a pedagogical phenomenon, basic competencies are not formed in students at the same time in the structure of a single academic subject. An integrative approach is required for its formation. Not only pedagogues, but also students' continuous actions related to acquiring knowledge and applying it in their practical activities, as well as activities aimed at eliminating internal and external obstacles, are important in the formation of basic competencies. The formation of basic competencies is an activity related to the student's application of acquired knowledge, turning it into personal experience. In order to successfully form basic competencies in students, it is necessary to present knowledge in a systematic, continuous, consistent and integrated manner with the help of certain strategies. Students should apply the knowledge they have acquired in a systematic and integrated manner to their practical activities.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The formation of various competencies in students requires pedagogical conditions:

- 1) creating favorable conditions for students' self-development, independent acquisition of knowledge and their application in practical activities during the educational process;
- 2) creating favorable conditions for students to acquire basic competencies with the help of integrated knowledge, supporting their practical activities.

Exercises and assignments are important in the formation of basic competencies in students with the help of integrative knowledge. In the pedagogical process, it is necessary to follow certain rules in the formation of basic competencies in students based on an integrative approach:

providing students with integrative knowledge, arming students with methods of applying this knowledge in their practical activities;

to pay attention to the external factors of the formation of basic competencies;

activation of personal experiences in the educational process, including conducting small studies, working on projects, activating practical skills, actively using communication methods, expanding the scope of independent learning and self-development;

self-development of students, such as regular analysis of their activities, understanding, choosing an independent trajectory of development, understanding the behavior and feelings of oneself and others, feeling the need for communication, following the rules of communication.

These expand the possibilities of relying on an integrative approach in the educational process. Internal pedagogical factors are important in the formation of basic competencies in students based on an integrative approach. The productivity of the student's thinking is reflected in the acceleration of the formation of basic competencies. This can be seen in the student's directions, aspirations, motives, rules, values, individual psychological qualities, and the uniqueness of his creative activity. In order to react to the objective reality, the subjects of the educational process should have a sufficient level of analytical activity experience. In this process, the following mental operations take an important place: thinking, rethinking, re-formation, being able to transfer specific methods of activity from one to another. Constructive, creative behavior of students ensures the transition from reflection to intellectual and personal level in problematic situations.

It is known that competence is manifested in the practical activity of a person. It is impossible to allow competence not to be demonstrated in the educational process. The formation of basic competencies in students is evident in the process of completing assignments. For this, it is appropriate to analyze the situations of working on educational tasks. Because in such situations, the competences formed by the student's flourish. Competences are displayed in harmony with the values formed by students.

For this, they must develop interest in a specific type of activity, the need to master it, and the desire to do so.

Practical activity is a product of a certain educational process or ability. Development of students' practical skills should be defined as the main goal when designing educational content based on the competency approach. Based on an integrative approach, the formation of basic competencies in students should form the logical basis of educational materials when choosing educational content. Situational tasks guide students to acquire practical skills. Each task is supposed to serve to form certain skills in students. For this purpose, it is required to define a set of situational tasks. Motivated situational assignments create the students' inclination to acquire basic competencies. In the process of solving the tasks, the pupils develop a tendency to acquire certain competencies.

CONCLUSION

In evaluating the effectiveness of the educational process based on the competence approach, it is necessary to base on new criteria: in this place, the answers of the students to the questions asked by the teachers are not evaluated, but the product created during the research and technological activities performed during the performance of control tasks is evaluated. It is of particular importance that students independently create the presented product in the process of individual or group activity.

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